

MODERN TRENDS IN IMPLEMENTATION OF TECHNOLOGIES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF CRITICAL THINKING IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract. In accordance with the trends of innovative development in the field of education in the world, special attention is paid to the improvement of the pre-school education system based on competency requirements. In particular, organization of high-quality educational services aimed at developing independent and creative thinking in children for the purposes of sustainable development set by UNESCO until 2030 has been noted as an urgent task. International experiences create the need to increase the effectiveness of the pedagogical process in preschool educational institutions, to introduce the basics of STEAM education from an early age, and to differentiate educational services.

Development of creative technologies aimed at increasing the psychophysiological, intellectual, creative and personal potential of children on a global scale, innovative education focused on the individual in preschool educational institutions Innovative education aimed at increasing the psychophysiological, intellectual, creative and personal potential of children on a global scale Scientific-practical research is being conducted on issues of improving the quality management mechanisms of pre-school education based on the principles of organization of learning environment and strategic management. In these studies, improvement of the information-methodological system of pre-school education management, differentiation of quality education services, introduction of information and communication technologies, interactive and problem-based teaching methods into the educational process, professional development of pre-school education system employees special attention is paid to the implementation of effective forms and methods of development and assessment of innovative competence.

Keywords: Cognitive process, education, tendency, critical thinking.

Scientist Jean-Jacques Piaget, who studied the thinking of preschool children, found that the thinking of a 6-7-year-old child has the following characteristics: children do

not have formed ideas about the space of the main properties of objects, that is, they do not understand the principle of conservation, they learn several properties of an object at the same time not taking into account and comparing their changes, centering, children ignore the rest and pay attention to only one thing, the most obvious feature. The phenomenon of centralization determines that the child cannot take into account other people's point of view, and his own view of the world appears to him as the only correct way. These features of children's thinking are clearly shown in the classic experiments of Jean Piaget. [5]

As the Chinese proverb goes: "Tell me and I'll forget." Show me and I will remember. Let me do it myself - and I will understand" - everything is strictly and learned for a long time when the child hears, sees and does it himself. 6-7-year-old children are interested in everything. They are new characterized by an incessant thirst for impressions, curiosity, a constant desire to experiment through trial and error, and independently search for new information about the world.

If we look at the term "criticism", it is very comprehensive, it is "Rpiro" meaning to distinguish, distinguish, and its structure has several types of branches, such as critical approach, critical analysis, critical evaluation, critical attitude, critical thinking. . In the scientific-methodical literature, it is defined as "criticism - research, discussion, analysis, ability to express an opinion, check, identify flaws without denying a certain content."

Critical thinking is one of the types of human intellectual activity, which is characterized by the objectivity of perception, understanding and approach to the surrounding information field. This is the ability to ask new, meaningful questions; development of various supporting arguments; making independent, thoughtful decisions.

Countries around the world use different educational technologies. We consider it important to show global trends and advanced foreign educational initiatives in the global education system.

In order to understand the nature and necessity of critical thinking in education, we will analyze the situation of several countries from the point of view of the educational system. The PISA international study shows that the Canadian education system shows high results in this direction. Education in Canada works like this: there is practically no federal education governance structure, education is autonomous. There is no national education policy or ministry of education in this country.

In 2016, the Canadian Council of Ministers of Education, after much discussion and research, adopted a draft of six global competencies: critical thinking and problem solving; innovation, creativity and entrepreneurship; learning skills, self-awareness and self-management; ability to cooperate; communication; orientation to global citizenship and sustainability. These six competencies allow children to acquire knowledge, including cognitive, social and personal skills, and apply knowledge in new and complex situations. Also, global competencies are included in the curriculum at all levels from kindergarten through 12th grade.

The "spirit of inquiry" permeates all levels of education, from kindergarten to the stage of thinking about professional careers. There are "achievement charts" that show the results of these competencies, which record not only information about children's learning activities and results, but also thinking and communication skills, as well as their application in various subject areas. There is also information about In non-formal education, students develop leadership and expressive skills.

Practices that develop 21st century competencies and are used in the Canadian education system: active learning practices, i.e. research, projects, experiential learning, practice, expanding physical and virtual connections with communities, computer literacy, environmental, medical data analysis, engineering, gaming, digital media creation, and robotics; knowledge that helps to exchange ideas, expose students to different ways of thinking, thereby developing critical and ethical thinking, preschool educational organizations encourage the creative use of various tools to engage students in small discussions in solving practical problems, participate in collaboration and research, and they feel their opinions are taken into account.

The next country we want to present for analysis is China. For us, China is of particular interest because it offers a transformative experience of education in a country with centuries-old cultural traditions that is not close to the European model in all respects.

However, at the same time, all the above universal competencies are also available within the framework of the Chinese education system. In 2014, the Ministry of Education published a report on transformational reform, including the development of universal competencies in all subjects. For example, the study of hieroglyphs in Chinese language classes is designed to help develop logical and critical thinking, analytical skills, aesthetic sensitivity, and creative abilities.

In Chinese education, universal competencies affect 3 areas: self-development, which implies subjectivity and autonomy, development of physical and psychological qualities, learning ability and learning process for individuals and groups. social inclusion, including relations between, in society and between countries; and the third area is cultural education, that is, understanding the achievements of human wisdom and civilization.

The role of the school in China is to adapt the general curriculum to the individual characteristics and needs of children.

The third case is the Republic of Korea, the ideal of an educated person. The Korean approach is characterized by the selection of "new literacies" integrated into interdisciplinary topics. Korean academic researchers have identified elements of universal competence within academic disciplines. In kindergarten, children's learning and success are constantly evaluated, for this purpose, special tasks, portfolios, self-assessment and mutual assessment methods of children are conducted.

Having studied the experiences of advanced foreign countries, we can conclude that one aspect of critical thinking is manifested in reflecting, perceiving and evaluating the opinions of others and one's own. The second aspect of critical thinking is related to knowledge. In this case, critical thinking performs evaluation tasks: the origin of knowledge, its reliability and validity are evaluated, knowledge is interpreted and understood, and conclusions or conclusions are drawn based on it.

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